

Enhanced engagement strategy

MATS Deliverable 6.2

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the European Union

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Summary

MATS wants to make a significant and meaningful contribution to improving the design and framing of trade policy at national, EU, African and global levels in view of achieving the SDGs. Evidence-based policy development and civil society and stakeholder dialogue play an important role throughout the lifetime of the project. This enhanced engagement strategy (D6.2) is the first update on the envisaged engagement with stakeholders since the start of the project more than half a year ago. It builds on the results of the Information Needs Assessment (D6.1), ongoing discussions on the design of the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub (D6.3) and the preparations of the stakeholder-civil society-policy dialogues (D6.4). The enhanced engagement strategy covers the following elements:

- i. Targeting of relevant actors for engagement.
- ii. Structured feedback loops with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), case study partners and policymakers involved in project activities.
- iii. Targeting of project outputs to current discourses and policy developments.
- iv. Using the most effective dissemination activities and forms.
- v. Monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities.

Deliverable title: Enhanced Engagement Strategy

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. Commission Services)

Introduction

MATS aims to identify key leverage points that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being. The project aims to augment previous studies by expanding the range and depth of investigation through a mixed-methods analysis and participatory engagement with policymakers, civil society, and the wider stakeholder community. To maximise its impact, MATS initiates and contributes to policy dialogues, participates in relevant fora, and provides cutting-edge information to decision-makers in private and public sectors.

Work package (WP) 6 (dialogue, dissemination, and exploitation) leads the activities that are to contribute to an enhanced civil society–stakeholder–policy dialogue. It promotes early and continuing engagement with relevant actors and organisations, in particular through an evidence-based communication platform – the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub – and a suite of communication activities.

The engagement strategy is based on the common experience that improved analyses and data are of little use if they do not effectively support more evidence-based decision-making and policy development. MATS therefore pays attention to an effective conversation with relevant actors from early on during implementation.

MATS aims at obtaining maximum benefit from effective engagement and collaboration between researchers, policymakers, civil society organizations (CSOs) and the wider stakeholder community. Throughout the project, a range of **discursive methods and tools** is used to foster collaboration. The project's '**Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub**' contributes to more informed exchanges and consultations. It serves as an online repository of resources and as a place where stakeholders can interact among themselves, and with the consortium. It strengthens the capacities for and aims at promoting evidence-based policymaking.

WP6 is dedicated to dialogue, dissemination, and exploitation. The main goal is to foster effective collaboration between researchers, policymakers, CSOs and the wider stakeholder community.

The related deliverables in WP6 are:

- Information Needs Assessment (D6.1)
- Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (D6.2)
- Interactive communication platform 'Sustainable Trade Hub' (D6.3)
- Suite of workshops, communication toolkit and dissemination materials in support of an enhanced civil society and policy dialogue (D6.4, D6.5, D7.3)

Components of the Engagement Strategy

MATS wants to make a significant and meaningful contribution to improving the design and framing of trade policy at national, EU, African and global levels in view of achieving the SDGs. Evidence-based policy development and civil society and stakeholder dialogue therefore play an important role throughout the lifetime of the project. The enhanced engagement strategy covers the following elements:

- i. Targeting of relevant actors for engagement.
- ii. Structured feedback loops with CSOs, case study partners and policymakers involved in project activities.
- iii. Targeting of project outputs to current discourses and policy developments.
- iv. Using the most effective dissemination activities and forms.
- v. Monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities.

Targeting of relevant actors for engagement

The enhanced engagement strategy is elaborated based on the results of the Information Needs Assessment (D6.1) and in consultation with consortium members in Task 6.4 (*Coordinate the implementation of all engagement and dissemination activities*).

The Information Needs Assessment built on initial contacts of more than 100 relevant actors of networks of different project partners, including SEATINI, TNI, OSOL, NWU, ESRF, CRPA, KE, AUA and UM (please see the complete name list of the project partners in Annex 1). It was the first step of engagement of participants of the three main target groups of MATS:

- i. The first target group are policymakers, actors from civil society and stakeholder organisations, and decision-makers in private production

and trade sectors actively involved in promoting and implementing sustainable agriculture trade at local, regional, national, EU, and international levels.

- ii. The second target group are members of the academic community involved in scientific research on the linkages between agricultural trade, investment, environmental sustainability, and human well-being.
- iii. The third target group are the potential beneficiaries of the policies and initiatives promoting trade sustainability. This will include the wider stakeholder community including actors in FVCs, and external experts in the fields of social and environmental sustainability.

The targeted relevant actors included the categories of Academics/Researchers, Agricultural Workers, Consumers associations, Farmers/Farmers Associations, Financial institutions, Government/Policy makers, Multilateral/International organisations, Non-Governmental Organisations, other Private Sector, Technical experts, and Traders. The type of actors reached with the survey identified themselves as research or academy (42%), followed by technical experts (19%) and nongovernmental organizations (19%). It is worth mentioning that actors directly involved in value chain activities – such as farmers, consumers, agricultural workers, traders, and other private sectors – had a lower presence, with consumers being the only category not represented in the responses. It is noted that this first consultation with key actors points to the need to broaden the MATS network so that a greater diversity of perspectives on agri-food trade are covered. In further activities attention therefore will be paid to the groups less represented so far, specifically representatives of farmers, consumers and the private sector.

Most of the respondents (65%) found their work relevant to MATS. Clustering the fields of work into three groups – see Figure 1 – reveal the linkages between broader fields such as agri-food trade and food systems transformation, with the enabling conditions for agri-food trade and the expected outcomes and sustainability impacts. Thus, actors whose work corresponds to food security and nutrition are usually also working on policies and governance, agri-food trade, or food systems transformation. The same happens with environmental sustainability and human well-being.

Figure 1: Field of work of respondents

The geographical scope of the respondents' work covers Europe, Africa, the Americas, and Asia, and its distribution largely reflects the location of MATS partners and case studies.

The outreach to stakeholders will be further enhanced in an incremental way through the following steps:

- i. Further engage with the respondents to the information needs assessment (D.6.1)
- ii. Incremental enrichment of the stakeholders' database with relevant civil society and stakeholders engaged in the WP3 (case studies), policymakers responsible for the institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks (WP4), as well as civil society, stakeholders and policymakers engaged in trade and sustainable development policy debates.
- iii. Linking with broader audiences through webinars (WP1-WP3-WP5)
- iv. Engagement with stakeholders through the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub (T6.2), Twitter and LinkedIn
- v. Call WP leads and Project Advisory Group (PAG) members to further enrich stakeholders list

Structured feedback loops with CSOs, case study partners and policymakers involved in the project

The Information Needs Assessment has shown stakeholders' interest in MATS, in improving the understanding of the interactions between agri-food trade, sustainability, and human well-being, and in the design of transition pathways toward sustainable agri-food trade. The main ways of interaction identified were 1) the dissemination of the results of case studies on the interactions between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being, 2) the dissemination of discussion papers and policy briefs related to the design of transition pathways towards sustainable agri-food trade, 3) practical guides to improve agri-food trade practices towards sustainability, and 4) the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub for joint work and discussions.

MATS aims at enhancing this engagement through the following main elements:

- i. Engagement through the **Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub** (T6.2).
- ii. Results of WP1-WP5 feed into **policy workshops** in Africa and Europe with consortium members and external experts representing research, policy, value chains actors and civil society.
- iii. **Webinars** and **online workshops** to collect CSO and policy feedback to research questions and processes (WP6, T6.3); and (online or real) events at national level to disseminate research results, feed relevant debates and discuss recommendations, related to the different case studies (WP3).
- iv. Transition pathways towards sustainable trade, and practices and policy-oriented outputs generated by MATS are subject to a thorough process of engagement, validation, and fine-tuning, based upon **peer-review** by consortium members, external experts, and stakeholders ensuring a diversity of perspectives and cross-fertilisation of views (WP5).

- v. Bridging the gaps between knowledge, improved civil society and stakeholder dialogue, and more evidence-based policies through **customised dissemination tools** adapted to the needs of users.
- vi. All consortium partners seek **active connections with relevant networks** and organisations, with a special focus to connect to policymakers, decision-makers in the private sector, civil society organizations, and practitioners in European and African countries and regions.

Table 1 summarises the main activities and tools proposed so far for implementing the Engagement Strategy.

Table 1
Activities and tools by type of user

I.	Policymakers and actors in CSOs (first target group)
	Database of 15 case studies – covering a large variety of sectors, markets, FSCs and contexts.
	Sustainable trade toolbox – frameworks, indicators and tools for a systemic analysis and assessment of the linkages between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being.
	Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub with all outcomes and knowledge (data, discussion papers, policy briefs, scientific publications, videos, research and innovation protocols etc.) generated in the project.
	Policy Briefs – co-created with public and private sectors decision-makers and civil society dialogue at high-level policy workshops.
	Specialist policy media and online seminars – webinars co-created with decision-makers reflect on for example experiences using the policy tools available; other policy media include e.g. publications on Politico.
	High profile Sustainable Trade Policy Forum – MATS organises an international event to showcase project results and outputs, and bring policymakers, CSOs and scientists together in facilitated sessions.
II.	Academic and educational community (second target group)
	Peer-reviewed publications – MATS showcases new concepts, pathways, regime and governance through theoretically driven analysis at academic events and in at least 8 international scientific journal articles.
	High profile international Sustainable Trade Policy Forum – as above.
III.	Potential beneficiaries (third target group)
	Case study briefs – showcasing output from empirical analyses and the related discussions.

Engagement with agricultural, rural and sustainability media – successful stories relating to trade case studies and the practical lessons learned for improving the benefits for farmers and other participants; articles in trade and farmer websites, newsletters and magazines.

Targeting of project outputs to current discourses and policy developments

The connections between trade and sustainable development are at the very heart of ongoing policy processes. This implies that our engagement strategy should make maximum use of the consultation processes that do exist globally, in the EU and Africa, and nationally. They include official public consultations, stakeholders' dialogues through national and European Economic and Social Committees, potential engagement with different market observatories in DG TRADE and DG Agri. At global level, MATS aims to contribute to peer reviewed expert processes, including those connected with the work of the High-Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) on Food Security and Nutrition (CFS). Specific Science-Policy Interface mechanism like the HLPE, The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) inform policy making processes. All these reports provide opportunities for external comments and contributions.

Food system transformation is high on the regional and international agendas, and different stakeholder networks are mobilising around related policy processes. They include:

- i. The discussions connected with the EU Green Deal and its Biodiversity, Farm to Fork, Deforestation or Fit for 55 strategies: They are the most elaborated EU response to achieving the SDGs. What their external impacts are and how trade rules need to be adapted to these new policy commitments remains unclear, and the MATS project aims to contribute to enhancing these discussions.

- ii. The new narrative on food systems put forward, including during the UN Food Systems Summit or at the CFS. The systemic approach gives more attention to sustainability and governance issues. The new dimension of agency of food security refers to the capacity of individuals or groups, the most vulnerable groups of society, to make decisions on food systems. Their engagement in policy processes shaping future food systems needs to be integrated in our engagement strategy.
- iii. The 'localisation' or territorial approaches agenda are becoming more prominent in the policy debates given the ongoing food and climate crises, pandemic and conflicts. Against the background of increasing hunger and inequalities, the role of international trade is more critically debated.
- iv. Standards at various levels are being intensively discussed, with numerous initiatives: Public standards such as the legislative initiative by the European Commission Sustainable Corporate Due Diligence, review of the Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) chapters in the Free Trade Agreements, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), deforestation-free supply chains, pesticide import tolerance; Public-private standards developed in multistakeholders initiatives, for example the Coalitions emerging from the UN Food Systems Summit or the Living Income Community of Practice. Private standards and specific commodity standards are evolving, for instance those for soybeans, palm oil or cocoa.

As part of the analysis of the linkages (WP3) and the institutional frameworks (WP4), further engagement with the stakeholders' networks will be developed. This will lead to the participatory design of transition pathways along the following two steps:

- i. **Step 1:** Visioning process involving stakeholders from the agricultural sector, civil society, policy and research. The aim is to discuss alternative futures and, eventually, to jointly develop visions of equitable economic partnerships in agricultural trade in support of a more sustainable, resilient food system (time horizon 2035+). In this

process, all involved parties are invited to contribute through interviews, online surveys and workshops.

- ii. **Step 2:** Formulation of higher-level transition pathways based on a participatory backcasting process (T5.2). This process builds on the results of Task 4.1 and T5.1 and identifies the required changes, incl. for local, regional, national and European authorities. More contextualised pathways are elaborated for 3-4 case studies (to be decided based on initial analyses, T3.2), illustrating desired futures and elaborating the concrete steps necessary to reach them.

The linkages between MATS and relevant policy processes on agricultural trade and sustainable development will need to be incrementally developed, by identifying case studies partners involvement in policy processes at national, regional or international levels (WP3), by exploring the relevant institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks (D4.5), in discussion papers on the political economy of trade regimes (D.4.3), and in our analyses on the policy coherence for sustainable development (D4.2).

This incremental approach will allow to further enrich outreach to key stakeholders involved, and the participation of a diversity of views in MATS outreach activities on transition pathways (WP5).

Project partners will continue to monitor reports and decisions of the different European institutions, and the role of international institutions and processes, both governmental and non-governmental, including the United Nations, FAO, UN Environment Programme (UNEP), SDG High Level Political Forum, World Trade Organization (WTO), World Economic Forum (WEF), International Organization for Standardization (ISO), Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCTA), Regional Economic Communities (REC), Economic Partnership Agreements (EPA) and various interest group associations.

Using the most effective dissemination activities and forms

The core instrument in MATS for connecting the project with relevant decision-makers, stakeholders and initiatives is the Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub (WP6, T6.2). The scope of the interactive platform is two-fold: to act as a centralised knowledge hub for the different stakeholders target audiences (see p. 5) interested in the project work; and to facilitate the discussions between such stakeholders.

Regarding its function as a data and knowledge resource, the interactive platform is the central provider of information for the project. It is designed in the first place for policymakers, civil society, value chain stakeholders and researchers. Its audience will further evolve according to the engagement activities as described above. It is a repository of information and knowledge stemming from the execution of the project's 15 case studies (WP3), the linkage mapping (WP1), the assessment toolbox (WP2, WP3), the analysis of institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks (WP4), the transition pathways (WP5) and information related to the civil society and policy dialogues (WP6). All will be made available in a format allowing users to have a quick overview of the different MATS deliverables and to delve further into the detailed data, analysis, related discussions.

Regularly updated news, especially from the 15 case studies, is provided – including through suitable social media communication channels such as Twitter and LinkedIn. Linkages to external data sources will be implemented and be made available allowing the stakeholders to link up with other relevant data sources, articles, policy documents, expert panels reports, CSO materials. The platform incorporates different types of data, including documents and reports, tabular data, statistical and analytical data, as well as geospatial data. As a one-stop-shop it will be linked to relevant external data sources and sites such as:

- Trade databases, such as the Trade Map of the International Trade Centre, World Bank's World Integrated Trade Solution, and the UN International Trade Database.
- Databases that comprise data from surveys and activities of international and national authorities, such as FAOSTAT and Eurostat.

- Information on agri-food trade regimes, practices and impacts from national authorities and NGOs approached during the project.

Equally important to its data management functionality are the platform's engagement and social discourse features. The project is already delivering different relevant outputs that could be shared more widely to our main target groups, and potentially contribute to a stakeholders' engagement to the MATS project. However, the design of the deliverables still needs to be adapted to reach larger audiences, through:

- i. short **Discussion Briefs** highlighting the main conclusions and discussion points for each deliverable in an accessible form hosted on the Sustainable Trade Hub. *See format in annex 2*
- ii. **adapted dissemination, participation and feedback activities.** The Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub is being designed as the main platform for outreach to stakeholders including the presentation of MATS deliverables and data, a visual dashboard, scenario support, feedback, and participation for stakeholders. This will be backed by other support activities, including social media, webinars and videos.

The Hub is designed for a user-friendly navigation with exhaustive search, link and data visualisation features. An interactive visual dashboard will be integrated, as a powerful interactive communication tool for analytical information and will allow to respond to specific requests of the visitor. Scenario support will be offered to project potential outcomes, interrelations and pathways according to the configurable parameters and visualized with diagrams/charts/tables.

Users will be able to build their data stories using different sets and facets of the available data and share them with other users within the platform. Users will also be able to share information with their broader communities via the production of downloadable reports and through their social media accounts via the direct share functionalities of the interactive platform.

Within the Hub's communication platform, discussion groups and threads based on MATS results and user data stories are supported, where all participants can provide their views, showcase evidence and insights via their

own data stories, and in general promote discourse for all aspects of sustainable trade. These groups will form the basis for structured feedback loops and participation in the discussions around the case studies (WP3), the design of transition pathways (WP5) and the stakeholders-civil society-policy dialogues (WP6).

Monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities

The progress of the dissemination and exploitation activities is monitored and evaluated on a six-monthly basis by the WP6 and project management teams based on a set of performance indicators (**Table 2.**). The effectiveness of the engagement strategy, activities and tools will be assessed based on this monitoring, and any barriers identified. If necessary, specific elements of the engagement strategy (as described in this document) will be adjusted, and the activities and tools refined to ensure an effective engagement of the different stakeholders.

Table 2

Performance indicators for dissemination and exploitation activities and tools

	Deadlines, activities and tools for dissemination and exploitation	Performance indicators
	Final version of Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy created by M10	1
First target group	Number of registered users in the Platform user database by M12	150
	Total number of entries in the Interactive Modelling Toolbox by M24	20-30
	Number of case studies workshops by M24	20-30
	Number of backcasting and transition pathways workshops by M30	5
	Number of Policy Briefs (in English) by M24	5
	Number of Policy Briefs translated in FR, DE, IT, ES, NL and PL by M28	3
	Number of Sustainable Trade Webinar in MATS YouTube channel by M30	5
	Number of articles in specialist policy media by M30	10
	Number of participants in Sustainable Trade Policy Forum by M 42	80
Second target group	Peer-reviewed articles in international scientific journals by M 42	8
Third target group	Number of case study reports and fact sheets online by M30	15
	Number of articles, essays, posts in stakeholder journals by M 42	20

All major project outputs are made available on the project's Sustainable Agri-Food Trade Hub. This includes presentations, recorded webinars, and publications, as well as case study abstracts, fact sheets, discussion briefs, policy briefs, etc.

Specific monitoring indicators for engagement will be linked to the Hub. Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) features will include the number of visits, number of users, time spent, navigation patterns, search patterns; scenario usage (scenario's built, parameters used); downloads; interactive engagement (number of registrations, comments left, participants in discussion/community fora). The relevant consent forms will be designed, and users will be informed on the usage of the collected data where applicable. In any case, MATS data handling will be in full compliance with GDPR and broader data regulation directives in the EC.

Annex 1. Complete List of Consortium Partners

- University of Helsinki (UH), Department of Economics and Management, Finland (project coordinator).
- KnowlEdge Srl (KE), Italy.
- Southern and Eastern Africa Trade Information and Negotiations Institute (SEATINI), Uganda.
- Research Centre on Animal Production, C.R.P.A. SPA, Department of Economics and Engineering (CRPA), Italy.
- SCiO – Big Data Analytics in Food Systems (SCiO), Greece.
- Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Spain.
- Transnational Institute (TNI), The Netherlands.
- The Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF), Tanzania.
- Oxfam Solidarité - Oxfam Solidariteit (OSOL), Belgium.
- Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI (FRAUNHOFER), Germany.
- Geononiko Panepistimion Athinon (AUA), Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, Greece.
- North-West University (NWU), TRADE Research Focus Area, South Africa.
- Universität Bern (UBERN), World Trade Institute, Switzerland.
- Maastricht University (UM), Faculty of Law, The Netherlands.

Annex 2

DISCUSSION BRIEFS X/2021

TITLE 1st ROW
SUBTITLE 1st ROW

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Introduction

Short description of the aim of the research question

Max: 2 para

Text here //

Highlights

Main highlights and conclusions of the research

(aim is to focus on the relevance to MATS objective: identify key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of trade on sustainable development and human rights.)

Max: 2 pages

Use of graphics, illustrations, highlights in box texts, ...

Text here //

Discussion points

Including: Limitations and assumptions/discussion points/evidence gaps/controversies and identify ways to address these

(aim is to identify relevant research and policy questions that can feed into the further research agenda and stakeholders-policy dialogue)

Max: 1 page

Text here //

For more information

Link to website and MATS research document

Link to request for more information about MATS/leave a message or reaction

Authors: